

PROPOSED PROTECTION AGAINST DIAGNOSTIC AND ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD (EMF) RADIATION DOSES IN HUMANS

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ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of advanced x-rays based radiological imaging for human diseases, and chiropractic and dental x-rays diagnostic technologies has helped in correctly diagnosing the diseases including skeletal and oral dysfunction. The effective dose to patients depends upon the type of diagnostic radiation procedure and technique. Increased risk of cancer occurs among those who received higher and more frequent doses of diagnostic radiation. It is important to recognize the growth of wireless communication technology which utilizes non-ionizing electromagnetic field (EMF) radiation at various frequencies, thus adds additional stressor to human health and wellness. The above-mentioned frequencies have produced hypersensitivity, a neoplastic and non-neoplastic diseases, neurological and non-neurological diseases. Diagnostic radiation increases free radicals by water hydrolysis, whereas EMF radiation enhances production of free radicals by increasing the activity of NADPH oxidase. Diagnostic radiation directly breaks DNA strands, whereas man-made polarized EMF radiation induces vibration in charged molecules which interferes with electrical communication between cells, which become very sensitive to external and internal stressors. EMF radiation at very high frequencies produces thermal effect which activates metabolism. To reduce damage from x-rays based medical devices and EMF radiation, the concepts of ALARA (as low as reasonably achievable) and PAMARA (protection as much as reasonably achievable) are proposed. Since some components of ALARA are difficult to implement for EMF radiation, we propose to implement PAMARA by consuming a mixture of micronutrients which would protection against both diagnostic and EMF radiation damage. Since oral and intestinal dysbiosis (increase in the number of harmful bacteria and decrease in the number of beneficial bacteria) are associated with diseases, consuming probiotics with prebiotics would reverse its harmful effects and thereby enhances the effectiveness of PAMARA in protecting against exposure from x-rays based medical devices and EMF radiation.

KEYWORDS: Diagnostic radiation; EMF radiation; Free radical damage; chronic inflammation. antioxidant protection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since 1980, average background radiation of 300 millirem/year (0.82 millirem/day) has not significantly changed, but diagnostic radiation exposure to individuals has nearly doubled in recent years. Radiation exposures from the medical sources have increased from 15% in the early 1980s to 50% today. Tomography (CT) scan alone contributes to 24% of all radiation exposures. The number of CT scans increased from 3 million per year in 1980 to over 50 million in the USA. No doubt, the use of CT scan and nuclear imaging technique have markedly

improved accuracy of diagnostic procedure and treatment of diseases (summarized from Harvard Health Publishing, 2024). The effective radiation doses delivered to patients, and radiation technologists can markedly vary depending upon the type of diagnostic radiation procedure. It is also important to understand that Radiation Technologist administering the x-ray or CT exposure is also susceptible to the scatter radiation from the multiple procedures they conduct per day.

The growth of advanced chiropractic and dental X-rays diagnostic technologies also has markedly increased. The use of new diagnostic procedures has markedly improved chiropractic and dental care. A typical dental x-ray exposes patients with radiation dose of 2-3 millirem. Estimated dose delivered to mouth by dental X-rays depends upon the types of dental x-ray devices such as Intraoral, Panoramic, Cephalometric, Cone beam computed tomography, and rectangular collimators. Chiropractic exposures depend on the region of the body being exposed. Upper Cervical Specific chiropractic techniques require multiple exposures for the diagnostic procedure, and an additional follow up exposure to prove the subluxation has been corrected. Other chiropractic techniques require full spine x rays and dosages will vary due to the density of the patient's body.

The advent of wireless communication technology which uses non-ionizing electromagnetic field (EMF) radiation of frequency 300 Hz to 300 GHz has added additional burden on human health. Exposure to EMF radiation emitted from the cell phone, laptop, Wi Fi microwaves, and the digital environment we live in, has become an unavoidably environmental risk, because it is present everywhere inside the house as well as out of the doors. Thus, it has become a necessity to reduce exposure from medical and dental diagnostic procedures as well as from EMF radiation emitted from wireless communication technology as much as possible to attenuate their adverse health effects. It is equally important to develop an effective biological plan to reduce the damaging effects these sources of ionizing and non-ionizing radiation on human health.

This review describes effective radiation doses delivered from medical, chiropractic, and dental diagnostic procedures, as well as EMF radiation, and their adverse health effects in humans. It also describes the concept of ALARA (as low as reasonably achievable) which is already being practiced in all Departments of Radiology, Chiropractic, and Dental offices world-wide. This review proposes implementation of ALARA for EMF radiation exposure. It also suggests a novel concept of PAMARA (protection as much as reasonably achievable) that would reduce damage from exposure to medical, chiropractic, and dental diagnostic procedures and EMF radiation by a micronutrient mixture containing multiple antioxidants. This review briefly describes the role of intestinal dysbiosis in initiation and progression of cancer and suggests that consuming probiotics with prebiotics would reverse the harmful effects of intestinal dysbiosis.

1. Estimated Effective Doses Delivered to Patients from Diagnostic Radiation Devices and Their Impact on Cancer Risk

Table 1 describes the doses delivered from various diagnostic procedures and probable risk of cancer. CT scan and nuclear cardiology examination can deliver doses between 10 mSv-100 mSv which can increase the risk of cancer (Mayo Clin Proc, 2021). A single CT scan

of abdomen delivers 10 mSv. Epidemiologic studies from atomic survivors and nuclear industry workers exposed to 10 mSv to 100 mSv have an increased risk of cancer.^[1,3] Others have reported no cancer risk below 100 mSv.^[4] Using the phosphorylated histone (γ -H2AX) as a measure of DNA double-strand break (DSB), it was demonstrated that patients receiving 10 mSv from one CT scan to thorax, abdomen or skull led to an increase in DSB in the lymphocytes continuously for 4-5 hrs. because of long lived free radical damage. DSB if not fully repaired can lead to cancer. Administration of a mixture of multiple antioxidants before CT scan reduced DSB by 58%.^[5] Supplementation with vitamin C or N-acetylcysteine (NAC) before coronary CT (< 3 mSv) or cardiac catheterization (> 9 mSv) reduce DSB by 87% and 43% respectively.^[6]

2. Estimated Radiation Doses from Upper Cervical Specific Chiropractic and Dental X rays Devices and Their Impact on Cancer Risk

A typical dental x-ray exposes patients with radiation dose of 2-3 millirem. Types of dental x-ray devices include Intraoral, Panoramic, Cephalometric, Cone beam computed tomography, and rectangular collimators. These devices deliver varying quantity of effective dose to the mouth (Table 2). The use of Rectangular collimators reduces effective dose by at least by 40% of those x-rays devices commonly used in dental care.^[7] Unfortunately, only 22% of dental offices uses this x-ray device. A review of several studies.^[8] has revealed that there was a positive correlation between exposure to dental x-ray and benign brain tumors such as meningioma.^[9,12] vestibular schwannoma.^[13] thyroid cancer.^[14,15] leukemia.^[16] In 2019, Dental offices in the USA contributed to 967 cases of cancer. Use of Rectangular Collimators can reduce the number cancer cases to 237. Despite this value, only 1% of Dental office uses this device.^[17] Dental x-rays can induce DNA damage and cytotoxic effects on oral mucosa cells.^[18,19] The effects of radiation doses emitted during chiropractic evaluation has not been carefully documented, but radiation dose delivered to patients and technician could be like dental x-ray.

3. Doses of EMF Radiation and Their Adverse Effects on Human Health

Non-ionizing EMF radiation has become an unavoidable environmental risk factor analogous to background radiation. Table 3 illustrates EMF radiation doses that have been used in the past and currently. The potential risk of this form of radiation is being debated despite support from solid experimental data and limited epidemiologic studies.

4.1. EMF radiation induces hypersensitivity in humans: The symptoms of hypersensitivity in humans include tinnitus, hyperacusis, dizziness, balance disorder, fibromyalgia, vegetative nerve dysfunction, and reduced cognitive capability, immediate memory loss, attention deficits, and eventually tempo-spatial confusion. These

symptoms were associated with chronic insomnia, fatigue, depressive tendency, anxiety emotional problem, and irritability.^[20,21]

4.2. EMF radiation induces cancer in humans: Several epidemiologic studies suggest that exposure to EMF radiation enhances the risk of glioma, acoustic neuroma, and meningioma. An elevated risk of these cancers has been associated with increasing latency, time of use, and with first exposure at the age 20 years and younger.^[22,24] Young women aged 21-39 years who were exposed to EMF radiation emitted from the Cell Phone kept in their brassieres at the rate of 10 h/day for several years developed excess incidence of multifocal invasive cancer in the area of the breast immediately adjacent to the cell phone.^[25] A few studies have reported no effect of EMF radiation emitted from mobile phones.^[26,31] The inconsistent results between authors could be due to utilization of different frequencies, dose (v/m), intensity (mT), and absorption of energy (W/Kg).

4.3. EMF radiation induces cancer in animals: The studies performed under The US National Toxicology Program (NTP) showed that EMF radiation exposure with 900 MHz in rats and with 1900 MHz to mice increased the incidence of tumor, especially glioma and malignant schwannoma. In addition, evidence of DNA damage was present in these organs.^[32,33] Exposure to EMF radiation with 1800 MHz at the highest dose of 50 V/m (volts/meter) increased the incidence of tumor of the brain and heart in rats.^[34]

4.4. EMF radiation induces non-neoplastic and non-neurological damage: A review of several studies reported that EMF radiation from Wi-Fi increased oxidative stress, sperm/testicular damage, apoptosis, DNA damage, endocrine changes, and calcium overload.^[35] EMF radiation enhanced production of free radicals by increasing the activity of reduced nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NADH) oxidase in the cell membrane.^[36] Female rats exposed to 1800 MHz led to eye damage attributed to upregulation of the expression of caspase-2 and P38MAPK (p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase) in ocular cells.^[37] Workers using mobile phones for 60 minutes showed increased systolic blood pressure compared to those who spent less time talking on the cell phones. Men exposed to EMF radiation showed an excess of blood pressure abnormalities, whereas women revealed more impairment of the ECG (electrocardiogram) profile.^[38]

5. Similarity and Difference Between Diagnostic Ionizing Radiation and EMF Non Ionizing Radiation
Both diagnostic and EMF radiation produce excessive amounts of free radicals, but they do so by different mechanisms. Ionizing radiation generates reactive oxygen species (ROS) by the hydrolysis of water, whereas EMF radiation enhances production of ROS by increasing activity of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) oxidase, a membrane-bound

enzyme complex which produces ROS from oxygen and NADPH. Ionizing radiation directly causes DNA strand breaks, whereas man-made polarized EMF radiation induce vibration in charged molecule in the body which can interfere with electric communication between cells, especially in the brain and heart. Vibrated molecules become very sensitive to external and internal stressors.^[39,41] EMF radiation at very high frequencies produces thermal effect which activates metabolism in the brain as evidenced by enhanced glucose metabolism.^[42,43]

Despite similarity and differences in mechanisms of action between diagnostic ionizing radiation EMF non-ionizing radiation, individual antioxidants appear to protect against both diagnostic radiation.^[5,44] and EMF radiation damage.^[45,48] There are several limitations of using a single antioxidant in protecting against diagnostic radiation or EMF radiation damage. They include (a) different antioxidants are distributed differently in the sub-cellular compartments of cells; therefore, a single antioxidant cannot protect all parts of the cell; (b) administered single antioxidant in a high oxidative environment created by diagnostic radiation exposure and EMF radiation becomes oxidized and then acts as a pro-oxidant rather than as an antioxidant; (c) an elevation of the levels of antioxidant enzymes and dietary and endogenous antioxidants is essential for reducing oxidative stress and inflammation, a single micronutrient cannot achieve this; (d) the affinity of different antioxidants for free radicals differs, depending upon their solubility; (e) both the aqueous and lipid compartments of the cell need to be protected together; a single antioxidant cannot meet this goal; and (f) vitamin E is more effective in quenching free radicals in a reduced oxygenated cellular environment, whereas vitamin C and alpha-tocopherol are more effective in a higher oxygenated environment of the cells.^[49] Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that administration of beta-carotene alone increased the risk of lung cancer in male heavy smokers.^[50] Vitamin E treatment was ineffective in patients with Alzheimer's disease.^[51,52] Vitamin E was ineffective in heart disease on primary and most secondary outcomes.^[53] Thus, it is unlikely that the use of single antioxidant would significantly reduce diagnostic radiation- or EMF radiation-induced damage.

6. Proposed Concept of ALARA (Protection as Much as Reasonably Achievable) for Diagnostic and EMF Radiation

The concept of ALARA is already practiced in the Department of Radiology world-wide. This concept is based on physical protection such as increasing the distance between radiation source and recipients, reducing exposure time, and providing lead shielding during exposure. Many components of ALARA used for reducing exposure to ionizing radiation is difficult to implement for EMF radiation. For example, the effectiveness of shielding from EMF radiation emitted

from the cell phone has been claimed by the commercial companies.^[54,55] However, Federal Trade Commission report suggests that shielding may interfere with the cell phone signal, which would draw even more power to communicate with the cell phone from tower (also called base station). This probably would expose individuals to more EMF radiation. Thus, shielding concept of ALARA is not applicable to EMF radiation. Proposed ALARA concept for EMF radiation suggests that reducing the distance between EMF radiation sources and users and time of exposure to EMF radiation environment would be possible, but users in most cases may not implement them. Another suggestion to reduce EMF radiation exposure would be to disconnect computer, printer, and Wi-Fi when not in use. Because of limitations of implementing some of the principles of ALARA against EMF radiation, the concept of PAMARA which would be equally applicable to both forms of radiation was developed.

7. Proposed Concept of PAMARA (Protection as Much as Reasonably Achievable) for Diagnostic and EMF

Radiation

A novel biological concept PAMARA for tissue protection against medical diagnostic and EMF radiation damage is proposed. This concept suggests that administration of a mixture of micronutrients to individuals who are likely to receive medical diagnostic ionizing radiation or EMF non-ionizing radiation may reduce its adverse health effects. A mixture of micronutrients containing vitamin A, mixed carotenoids, vitamin C, alpha-tocopheryl acetate, alpha-tocopheryl

succinate, vitamin D3, alpha-lipoic acid, n-acetylcysteine, coenzyme Q10, curcumin, resveratrol, quercetin, green tea extract, all B-vitamins, selenomethionine, and zinc is proposed. This mixture would increase the levels of antioxidant enzymes by activating a nuclear transcriptional factor Nrf2 and the levels of dietary and endogenous antioxidant compounds. Antioxidants in this mixture would donate electron to charge positively charged particles which would lessen vibration and thereby reduce damage. Thus, implementation of PAMARA may provide an optimal tissue protection against diagnostic radiation as well as EMF radiation. Preclinical and clinical studies should be performed to test the validity the proposed concepts of biological protection against diagnostic ionizing radiation and EMF non-ionizing radiation.

8. Intestinal Dysbiosis and Cancer

Intestinal dysbiosis participates in the development and progression of colorectal cancer.^[56] lung cancer.^[57] prostate cancer.^[58] acute leukemia.^[59] and breast cancer.^[60] It is likely that the intestinal dysbiosis may increase the risk of diagnostic x-ray exposure and EMF radiation-induced cancer. Therefore, consumption of probiotics with prebiotics may reverse the above harmful effects of intestinal dysbiosis.

9. Implementation of PAMARA

Based on the studies discussed above, we propose that combination with a micronutrient mixture and probiotics with prebiotics together may reduce the risk of cancer from exposure to high diagnostic ionizing radiation and EMF non-ionizing radiation doses at the same time.

Table 1: Dose ranges and terminology for describing the excess lifetime risks of cancer incidence from different medical diagnostic procedures for adult patients of average age (30–39 years).

Effective doses (mSv)	Risk of cancer inferred from LNT model ²	Proposed term for dose level	Examples of medical radiation procedures within different dose categories
<0.1	<10 ⁻⁵	Negligible	Radiographs of chest, femur, shoulder limbs, neck, and teeth
0.1–1	10 ⁻⁵ –10 ⁻⁴	Minimal or extremely low	Radiographs of spine and trunk, and ^{99m} Tc lung ventilation and renal imaging
1–10	10 ⁻⁴ –10 ⁻³	Very low	CT scans of head and body, cardiac angiography, and a variety of nuclear medicine examinations
10–100	10 ⁻³ –10 ⁻²	Low	Multiple CT scans of trunk with contrast and higher dose interventional procedures
100 s	>10 ⁻² based on epidemiology	Moderate	Multiple procedures and follow-up studies

LNT, linear no-threshold; CT, computed tomography.

Table 2: Effective doses delivered by various Dental x-ray imaging devices.

Type of devices	effective dose
Intraoral radiography	1.3 μSv
Panorama	17.93 μSv
CBCT	121 μSv
Cephalometric x-rays	5.03 μSv
CBCT= Cone beam computed tomography	
From. ^[62,63]	

Table 3: Operating frequencies range of wireless communications devices.

Types of devices.	Frequency range
RF-EMF radiation	3 KHz - 300 GHz
EL-EMF radiation	0-300 Hz
5 G	3-300 GHz
4G	2-8 GHz
3G	1885- 2200 MHz
2G	800-1900 MHz
1G	450 MHz
WI-FI	2.4 GHz
Mobil phone models	1800 – 2200 MHz
Laptops	1000 – 3600 MHz

G = Generation

RF-EMF = Radiofrequency -Electromagnetic field. Transfer of energy by radio waves

ELF-EMF = Extremely low frequency-electromagnetic field

Brief Bio-sketch of Kedar N Prasad, PhD

Kedar N. Prasad obtained a master's degree in Zoology from the University of Bihar in India in 1956, and a Ph.D. degree in Radiation Biology from the University of Iowa, Iowa City in 1963. He went to the Brookhaven National Laboratory, Long Island, New York, for a Post-doctoral training in Parkinson disease in 1964. He joined the Department of Radiology at the University of Colorado School of Medicine in 1968 where he became Professor and Director for the Center for Vitamins and Cancer Research. In 2004, he took an early retirement to be with his family in California.

Publications: During his distinguished career, he has published over 250 papers in peer-reviewed journals including Nature, Science, and Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences (PNAS). His research was funded by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) for over 30 years.

Books: He authored or edited 33 books on radiobiology, neurodegenerative disease, and nutrition and cancer. He has also written books on Diabetes, Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson disease, and PTSD and Traumatic Brain Injury for the consumers.

Major discoveries: In 1971, he discovered that an elevation of cyclic AMP induced terminal differentiation in neuroblastoma cells in culture. These normal-looking neurons when injected into animals did not produce tumor. In 1971, he discovered that butyric acid as a potent anti-cancer agent in neuroblastoma cells in culture. In 1982, he discovered that alpha-tocopheryl succinate as a potent anti-cancer agent in melanoma cells in culture. In 2020, he proposed that high dose multiple antioxidants kill cancer cells but not normal cells by blocking uptake of glucose and glutamine in cancer cells.

Membership in scientific organizations: He had been a member of numerous professional organizations and served as an ad-hoc member of various Study Sections of the National Institute of Health.

Invited speakers: He was frequently invited to speak at the several National and International meetings including very prestigious conferences, such as Princess Takamatsu Cancer Conference in Tokyo, Cold Spring Harbor meeting on Differentiation of Cancer Cells in Long Island, New York; and NATO Conference on Radiation Protection in Kiev, Ukraine.

Honors: In 1982, he was invited by the Nobel Prize Committee to nominate a candidate for the Nobel Prize in Medicine.

In 2017, he was invited to become a member of the Royal Society of Medicine, London

During 1994-2002, he was the President of the International Society for Nutrition and Cancer.

Currently, he serves as a Chief Scientific Officer of the Engage Global, Inc. Provo, Utah.

10. CONCLUSIONS

The growth of advanced radiological imaging, chiropractic, and dental x-rays diagnostic technologies has been very useful in making correct diagnosis and improving the treatment of the diseases. The effective radiation doses received by the patients depends upon the type of diagnostic radiation procedure. The risk of cancer in those who received higher doses of diagnostic radiation increases. The rapid development of wireless communication technology which uses non-ionizing electromagnetic field (EMF) radiation of frequencies varying from 300 Hz to 300 GHz constitutes an additional environmental stressor for human health. It produces hypersensitivity and neoplastic and non-neoplastic diseases as well non-neurological diseases. Both diagnostic and EMF radiation produce excessive amounts of free radicals, but they do so by different mechanism. Ionizing radiation do so by causing hydrolysis of water, whereas EMF radiation causes by increasing the activity of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) oxidase which produces ROS from oxygen and NADPH. Diagnostic radiation breaks DNA strands, whereas man-made polarized EMF radiation induces vibration in charged molecules which interferes with electric communication between cells which are easily damaged by external and

internal stressors. To reduce exposure from medical and dental diagnostic devices, the concept of ALARA (as low as reasonably achievable) has been in use for reducing exposure from ionizing radiation in the Department of Radiology. This concept is based on physical protection such as increasing the distance between radiation source and recipients, reducing exposure time, and providing lead shielding during exposure. Some components of ALARA are difficult to implement for EMF radiation. For example, shielding of cell phone may interfere with the signal which would draw even more power to communicate with the cell phone to tower (also called base station). This may result in exposing individuals to more EMF radiation. Because of limitations of utilizing the principles of ALARA against EMF radiation, the concept of PAMARA (protection as much as reasonably achievable) which would be equally applicable to both forms of radiation was developed. This novel concept suggests that administration of a mixture of micronutrients would increase the levels of antioxidant enzymes by activating a nuclear transcriptional factor Nrf2 and the levels of dietary and endogenous antioxidant compounds. Enhancing the levels of both antioxidant enzymes and antioxidant compounds are essential for simultaneously reducing oxidative stress and chronic inflammation. Antioxidants in this mixture may reduce number of charged particles by donating an electron to a positively charged particles making them neutral and reducing the effects of vibration. These cellular changes are essential for optimal tissue protection against diagnostic radiation as well as EMF radiation. Preclinical and clinical studies should be performed to test the validity the proposed concept of biological protection. Since intestinal dysbiosis participates in the development and progression of cancer irrespective of causes, consuming probiotics with prebiotic may reduce the risk of developing cancer after exposure to diagnostic and EMF radiation. To implement the concept of PAMARA, we propose that a micronutrient mixture and probiotics with prebiotics together would reduce the risk of cancer after exposure to diagnostic and EMF radiation.

REFERENCES

- Pierce DA, Preston DL. Radiation-related cancer risks at low doses among atomic bomb survivors. *Radiat Res.* 2000; 154(2): 178-86.
- Preston DL, Ron E, Tokuoka S, Funamoto S, Nishi N, Soda M, et al. Solid cancer incidence in atomic bomb survivors: 1958-1998. *Radiat Res.*, 2007; 168(1): 1-64.
- Cardis E, Vrijheid M, Blettner M, Gilbert E, Hakama M, Hill C, et al. The 15-Country Collaborative Study of Cancer Risk among Radiation Workers in the Nuclear Industry: estimates of radiation-related cancer risks. *Radiat Res.*, 2007; 167(4): 396-416.
- Tubiana M, Feinendegen LE, Yang C, Kaminski JM. The linear no-threshold relationship is inconsistent with radiation biologic and experimental data. *Radiology*, 2009; 251(1): 13-22.
- Kuefner MA, Brand M, Ehrlich J, Braga L, Uder M, Semelka RC. Effect of antioxidants on X-ray-induced gamma-H2AX foci in human blood lymphocytes: preliminary observations. *Radiology*, 2012; 264(1): 59-67.
- Stehli J, Fuchs TA, Ghadri JR, Gaemperli O, Fiechter M, Kaufmann PA. Antioxidants prevent DNA double-strand breaks from X-ray-based cardiac examinations: a randomized, double-blinded, placebo-controlled trial. *J Am Coll Cardiol*, 2014; 64(1): 117-8.
- Shetty A, Almeida FT, Ganatra S, Senior A, Pacheco-Pereira C. Evidence on radiation dose reduction using rectangular collimation: a systematic review. *Int Dent J.* 2019; 69(2): 84-97.
- Hwang SY, Choi ES, Kim YS, Gim BE, Ha M, Kim HY. Health effects from exposure to dental diagnostic X-ray. *Environ Health Toxicol.* 2018; 33(4): e2018017.
- Preston-Martin S, Paganini-Hill A, Henderson BE, Pike MC, Wood C. Case-control study of intracranial meningiomas in women in Los Angeles County, California. *J Natl Cancer Inst.*, 1980; 65(1): 67-73.
- Rodvall Y, Ahlbom A, Pershagen G, Nylander M, Spannare B. Dental radiography after age 25 years, amalgam fillings and tumours of the central nervous system. *Oral Oncol*, 1998; 34(4): 265-9.
- Claus EB, Calvocoressi L, Bondy ML, Schildkraut JM, Wiemels JL, Wrensch M. Dental x-rays and risk of meningioma. *Cancer.* 2012; 118(18): 4530-7.
- Lin MC, Lee CF, Lin CL, Wu YC, Wang HE, Chen CL, et al. Dental diagnostic X-ray exposure and risk of benign and malignant brain tumors. *Ann Oncol.* 2013; 24(6): 1675-9.
- Han YY, Berkowitz O, Talbott E, Kondziolka D, Donovan M, Lunsford LD. Are frequent dental x-ray examinations associated with increased risk of vestibular schwannoma? *J Neurosurg.* 2012; 117: 78-83.
- Memon A, Godward S, Williams D, Siddique I, Al-Saleh K. Dental x-rays and the risk of thyroid cancer: a case-control study. *Acta Oncol.* 2010; 49(4): 447-53.
- Neta G, Rajaraman P, Berrington de Gonzalez A, Doody MM, Alexander BH, Preston D, et al. A prospective study of medical diagnostic radiography and risk of thyroid cancer. *Am J Epidemiol.* 2013; 177(8): 800-9.
- Nishi M, Miyake H. A case-control study of non-T cell acute lymphoblastic leukaemia of children in Hokkaido, Japan. *J Epidemiol Community Health.* 1989; 43(4): 352-5.
- Benn DK, Vig PS. Estimation of x-ray radiation related cancers in US dental offices: Is it worth the risk? *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol.* 2021; 132(5): 597-608.

18. Cerqueira EM, Gomes-Filho IS, Trindade S, Lopes MA, Passos JS, Machado-Santelli GM. Genetic damage in exfoliated cells from oral mucosa of individuals exposed to X-rays during panoramic dental radiographies. *Mutat Res.*, 2004; 562(1-2): 111-7.
19. Li G, Yang P, Hao S, Hu W, Liang C, Zou BS, et al. Buccal mucosa cell damage in individuals following dental X-ray examinations. *Sci Rep.*, 2018; 8(1): 2509.
20. Belpomme D, Irigaray P. Electrohypersensitivity as a Newly Identified and Characterized Neurologic Pathological Disorder: How to Diagnose, Treat, and Prevent It. *Int J Mol Sci.*, 2020; 21(6).
21. Johansson A, Nordin S, Heiden M, Sandstrom M. Symptoms, personality traits, and stress in people with mobile phone-related symptoms and electromagnetic hypersensitivity. *J Psychosom Res.* 2010; 68(1): 37-45.
22. Miller AB, Morgan LL, Udasin I, Davis DL. Cancer epidemiology update, following the 2011 IARC evaluation of radiofrequency electromagnetic fields (Monograph 102). *Environ Res.* 2018; 167: 673-83.
23. Hardell L, Carlberg M, Soderqvist F, Mild KH. Pooled analysis of case-control studies on acoustic neuroma diagnosed 1997-2003 and 2007-2009 and use of mobile and cordless phones. *Int J Oncol.* 2013; 43(4): 1036-44.
24. Hardell L, Carlberg M. Mobile phone and cordless phone use and the risk for glioma - Analysis of pooled case-control studies in Sweden, 1997-2003 and 2007-2009. *Pathophysiology.* 2015; 22(1): 1-13.
25. West JG, Kapoor NS, Liao SY, Chen JW, Bailey L, Nagourney RA. Multifocal Breast Cancer in Young Women with Prolonged Contact between Their Breasts and Their Cellular Phones. *Case Rep Med.* 2013; 2013: 354682.
26. Karipidis K, Elwood M, Benke G, Sanagou M, Tjong L, Croft RJ. Mobile phone use and incidence of brain tumour histological types, grading or anatomical location: a population-based ecological study. *BMJ Open.* 2018; 8(12): e024489.
27. Nilsson J, Jaras J, Henriksson R, Holgersson G, Bergstrom S, Estenberg J, et al. No Evidence for Increased Brain Tumour Incidence in the Swedish National Cancer Register Between Years 1980-2012. *Anticancer Res.* 2019; 39(2): 791-6.
28. Vila J, Turner MC, Gracia-Lavedan E, Figuerola J, Bowman JD, Kincl L, et al. Occupational exposure to high-frequency electromagnetic fields and brain tumor risk in the INTEROCC study: An individualized assessment approach. *Environ Int.*, 2018; 119: 353-65.
29. Aydin D, Feychting M, Schuz J, Tynes T, Andersen TV, Schmidt LS, et al. Mobile phone use and brain tumors in children and adolescents: a multicenter case-control study. *J Natl Cancer Inst.*, 2011; 103(16): 1264-76.
30. Schuz J, Bohler E, Berg G, Schlehofer B, Hettinger I, Schlaefer K, et al. Cellular phones, cordless phones, and the risks of glioma and meningioma (Interphone Study Group, Germany). *Am J Epidemiol.* 2006; 163(6): 512-20.
31. Lonn S, Ahlbom A, Hall P, Feychting M, Swedish Interphone Study G. Long-term mobile phone use and brain tumor risk. *Am J Epidemiol.* 2005; 161(6): 526-35.
32. Li CW, Lai YJ, Hsu JL, Hung MC. Activation of phagocytosis by immune checkpoint blockade. *Front Med.* 2018; 12(4): 473-80.
33. Melnick RL. Commentary on the utility of the National Toxicology Program study on cell phone radiofrequency radiation data for assessing human health risks despite unfounded criticisms aimed at minimizing the findings of adverse health effects. *Environ Res.*, 2019; 168: 1-6.
34. Falcioni L, Bua L, Tibaldi E, Lauriola M, De Angelis L, Gnudi F, et al. Report of final results regarding brain and heart tumors in Sprague-Dawley rats exposed from prenatal life until natural death to mobile phone radiofrequency field representative of a 1.8GHz GSM base station environmental emission. *Environ Res.* 2018; 165: 496-503.
35. Pall ML. Wi-Fi is an important threat to human health. *Environ Res.* 2018; 164: 405-16.
36. Yahyazadeh A, Deniz OG, Kaplan AA, Altun G, Yurt KK, Davis D. The genomic effects of cell phone exposure on the reproductive system. *Environ Res.* 2018; 167: 684-93.
37. Eker ED, Arslan B, Yildirim M, Akar A, Aras N. The effect of exposure to 1800 MHz radiofrequency radiation on epidermal growth factor, caspase-3, Hsp27 and p38MAPK gene expressions in the rat eye. *Bratisl Lek Listy.* 2018; 119(9): 588-92.
38. Szyjkowska A, Gadzicka E, Szymczak W, Bortkiewicz A. [The reaction of the circulatory system to stress and electromagnetic fields emitted by mobile phones - 24-h monitoring of ECG and blood pressure]. *Med Pr.* 2019; 70(4): 411-24.
39. Panagopoulos DJ. Polarization: A key difference between man-made and natural electromagnetic fields, in regard to biological activity. *Sci Rep.* 2015; 5: 14914.
40. Kivrak EG, Yurt KK, Kaplan AA, Alkan I, Altun G. Effects of electromagnetic fields exposure on the antioxidant defense system. *J Microsc Ultrastruct.* 2017; 5(4): 167-76.
41. Panagopoulos DJ, Karabarbounis A, Yakymenko I, Chrousos GP. Human-made electromagnetic fields: Ion forced-oscillation and voltage-gated ion channel dysfunction, oxidative stress and DNA damage (Review). *Int J Oncol.* 2021; 59(5).
42. Son Y, Kim JS, Jeong YJ, Jeong YK, Kwon JH, Choi HD, et al. Long-term RF exposure on behavior and cerebral glucose metabolism in 5xFAD mice. *Neurosci Lett.* 2018; 666: 64-9.
43. Volkow ND, Tomasi D, Wang GJ, Vaska P, Fowler JS, Telang F, et al. Effects of cell phone radiofrequency signal exposure on brain glucose metabolism. *JAMA.* 2011; 305(8): 808-13.

44. Prasad KN, editor. Micronutrients in protecting against late adverse effects of diagnostic radiation doses. Boca Raton, FL: CRC press/Francis & Taylor Publishing Groups; 2011.
45. Petitdant N, Lecomte A, Robidel F, Gamez C, Blazy K, Villegier AS. Cerebral radiofrequency exposures during adolescence: Impact on astrocytes and brain functions in healthy and pathologic rat models. *Bioelectromagnetics*. 2016; 37(5): 338-50.
46. Erdem Koc G, Kaplan S, Altun G, Gumus H, Gulsum Deniz O, Aydin I, et al. Neuroprotective effects of melatonin and omega-3 on hippocampal cells prenatally exposed to 900 MHz electromagnetic fields. *Int J Radiat Biol*. 2016; 92(10): 590-5.
47. Pastaci Ozsobaci N, Duzgun Ergun D, Durmus S, Tuncdemir M, Uzun H, Gelisgen R, et al. Selenium supplementation ameliorates electromagnetic field-induced oxidative stress in the HEK293 cells. *J Trace Elem Med Biol*. 2018; 50: 572-9.
48. Lewicka M, Henrykowska G, Zawadzka M, Rutkowski M, Pacholski K, Buczynski A. Impact of electromagnetic radiation emitted by monitors on changes in the cellular membrane structure and protective antioxidant effect of vitamin A - In vitro study. *Int J Occup Med Environ Health*. 2017; 30(5): 695-703.
49. Vile GF, Winterbourn CC. Inhibition of adriamycin-promoted microsomal lipid peroxidation by beta-carotene, alpha-tocopherol and retinol at high and low oxygen partial pressures. *FEBS Lett*. 1988; 238(2): 353-6.
50. Albanes D, Heinonen OP, Huttunen JK, Taylor PR, Virtamo J, Edwards BK, et al. Effects of alpha-tocopherol and beta-carotene supplements on cancer incidence in the Alpha-Tocopherol Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention Study. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 1995; 62(6 Suppl): 1427S-30S.
51. Isaac MG, Quinn R, Tabet N. Vitamin E for Alzheimer's disease and mild cognitive impairment. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2008(3): CD002854.
52. Sano M, Ernesto C, Thomas RG, Klauber MR, Schafer K, Grundman M, et al. A controlled trial of selegiline, alpha-tocopherol, or both as treatment for Alzheimer's disease. The Alzheimer's Disease Cooperative Study. *N Engl J Med*. 1997; 336(17): 1216-22.
53. Heart Outcomes Prevention Evaluation Study I, Yusuf S, Dagenais G, Pogue J, Bosch J, Sleight P. Vitamin E supplementation and cardiovascular events in high-risk patients. *N Engl J Med*. 2000; 342(3): 154-60.
54. Panagopoulos DJ, Chrousos GP. Shielding methods and products against man-made Electromagnetic Fields: Protection versus risk. *Sci Total Environ*. 2019; 667: 255-62.
55. Leitgeb N, Cech R. Electromagnetic shielding mats: facts and fiction. *Radiat Prot Dosimetry*. 2007; 123(4): 450-6.
56. Wong CC, Yu J. Gut microbiota in colorectal cancer development and therapy. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol*. 2023; 20(7): 429-52.
57. Zhuang H, Cheng L, Wang Y, Zhang YK, Zhao MF, Liang GD, et al. Dysbiosis of the Gut Microbiome in Lung Cancer. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol*. 2019; 9: 112.
58. Zhong W, Wu K, Long Z, Zhou X, Zhong C, Wang S, et al. Gut dysbiosis promotes prostate cancer progression and docetaxel resistance via activating NF-kappaB-IL6-STAT3 axis. *Microbiome*. 2022; 10(1): 94.
59. Zhou Y, Zhou C, Zhang A. Gut microbiota in acute leukemia: Current evidence and future directions. *Front Microbiol*. 2022; 13: 1045497.
60. Zhang J, Xie Q, Huo X, Liu Z, Da M, Yuan M, et al. Impact of intestinal dysbiosis on breast cancer metastasis and progression. *Front Oncol*. 2022; 12: 1037831.
61. Martin CJ. Effective dose in medicine. *Ann ICRP*. 2020; 49(1_suppl): 126-40.
62. Signorelli L, Patcas R, Peltomaki T, Schatzle M. Radiation dose of cone-beam computed tomography compared to conventional radiographs in orthodontics. *J Orofac Orthop*. 2016; 77(1): 9-15.
63. Lee H, Badal A. A Review of Doses for Dental Imaging in 2010-2020 and Development of a Web Dose Calculator. *Radiol Res Pract*. 2021; 2021: 6924314.